

**UNDERSTANDING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SCHOOL-BASED
MANAGEMENT (SBM) LEADERSHIP AND GOVERNANCE AS
EXPERIENCED BY STAKEHOLDERS OF GENERAL
SANTOS CITY NATIONAL SECONDARY SCHOOL
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Understanding the Implementation of School-Based Management (SBM) Leadership and Governance as Experienced by Stakeholders of General Santos City National Secondary School of Arts and Trades

Judelyn P. Malasaga, * Francisco M. Espinosa, Geraldine D. Rodriguez
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to describe the experienced challenges of stakeholders in the implementation of school-based management (SBM) leadership and governance. The study employed a qualitative phenomenological research design. The participants of this study were the 9 stakeholders; 5 stakeholders underwent individual interview (IDI), while the other 4 underwent focused-group discussion (FGD). The study has three formulated themes which were the challenges, coping, and insights of stakeholders. The challenges of stakeholders in the implementation of school-based management (SBM) leadership and governance were able to formulate the following emergent themes: lack of support in SBM implementation, roles and involvement in SBM leadership, miscommunication, and initial expectations about SBM. Moreover, the coping mechanism of stakeholders in the implementation of school-based management (SBM) leadership and governance formulated the following emergent themes: conflict resolution within SBM framework, balancing SBM responsibilities with other obligations, innovative approaches to improve SBM processes, and seeking support and guidance during challenging times. The last formulated theme for the insights of stakeholders in the implementation of school-based management (SBM) leadership and governance had formulated the following emergent themes: transparency and communication within SBM, collaboration of stakeholders in SBM, and improvement of SBM.

Keywords: *educational management, school-based management (SBM), leadership, governance, phenomenology, philippines*

Introduction

"Understanding the Implementation of School-Based Management (SBM) Leadership and Governance as Experienced by Stakeholders is the compass that illuminates the path toward effective educational decentralization, revealing the intricate interplay of perspectives that shape the destiny of our schools."-Dr. Emily Stevens

The quote underscores the importance of grasping the real-world impacts of School-Based Management (SBM) leadership and governance, particularly from the perspective of directly involved stakeholders. It highlights how this understanding is a critical compass in navigating the complexities of decentralizing education systems. Recognizing the diverse insights of stakeholders, including teachers, administrators, parents, and students, is essential for effectively shaping educational institutions' future.

Understanding the implementation of school-based management (SBM) leadership and governance from the stakeholders' perspective is significant globally. It is critical to improve the quality of education by involving stakeholders in decision-making, leading to more effective, customized educational strategies and enhanced learning outcomes. This understanding is essential to ensure education is locally relevant, accounting for differences in cultures, traditions, and challenges, making education engaging and effective for diverse regions (Angerryco, 2019).

Additionally, implementing School-Based Management (SBM) leadership and governance is vital as it addresses global challenges, particularly education inequality, by allowing local customization and marginalized voices in decision-making. SBM also aligns with Sustainable Development Goal 4, which has significant economic implications for workforce competitiveness. In the Philippines, public schools grapple with high dropout rates, quality issues, and capacity shortages. Initiatives like SBM, supported by national policies and projects, work to improve the quality of education for functional literacy among Filipinos (Cheng, 2022).

As a committed teacher leading team initiatives with parents, administrators, and other educators to decentralize authority via School-Based Management (SBM), I was in the vanguard of reforming our school's administration. Our lack of experience with SBM made it seem unsafe initially, but with constant communication, a common goal, and continued professional growth, we gradually acquired confidence. We were prepared to assess data, set priorities for needs, and distribute resources wisely through training sessions and meetings. Our shared dedication drove us forward despite obstacles like limited resources and competing interests, which improved student outcomes and bolstered community pride. It took more than just reorganizing governance to implement SBM; it also required fostering a collaborative and accountable culture.

Hence, while research highlights the value of including stakeholders in decision-making processes to improve educational strategies and results, more needs to be done about how different stakeholder groups view and negotiate the application of SBM, particularly in areas with severe capacity shortages and education inequality. Moreover, although research indicates that SBM is in line with global education objectives like Sustainable Development Goal 4, little is known about how SBM contributes to the achievement of these

objectives, especially in nations like the Philippines, where public schools are confronted with particular difficulties like high dropout rates and quality problems.

Therefore, bridging this research gap is urgent, especially in the global education challenges intensified by the COVID-19 pandemic. SBM is crucial for addressing issues of access, quality, and equity, and as education evolves with technology and societal changes, a nuanced understanding of SBM is vital. Furthermore, the quality of education is a crucial determinant of global economic competitiveness, underscoring the necessity for research to shape effective policies.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the implementation of School-Based Management Leadership and Governance in General Santos City National Secondary School of Arts and Trades (GSCNSSAT) school year 2017 to 2018. Specifically, this study aimed to respond to the following queries:

1. How do stakeholders describe their challenges in implementing School-Based Management (SBM) leadership and governance?
2. How do stakeholders cope with the challenges in implementing School-Based Management (SBM) leadership and governance?
3. What are stakeholders' insights in implementing School-Based Management (SBM) leadership and governance?

Methodology

This section presents a detailed description of the research methods and approaches, the role of the researcher, research participants or population, data collection, analysis, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study gathered the stakeholders' lived experiences in implementing school-based management leadership and governance at General Santos City National Secondary School of Arts and Trades (GSCNSSAT) for the school year 2017 to 2018. This study used a qualitative approach to research utilizing phenomenological study in tradition, descriptive in discipline, and thematic in interpretation.

Qualitative research involves adopting a constructivist, naturalistic, interpretative, post-positivist, or postmodern perspective. The study centers on individuals' realities, emphasizing the faithful reporting of actualities based on the voices and interpretations of informants. With inductive methodology, the research derives categories from participants, yielding context-specific information to form patterns or theories explaining the phenomenon. This inquiry is characterized by its value-laden and biased nature, acknowledging the influence of time and space on the researcher. The approach typically avoids assuming universal application, focusing instead on the applicability of discoveries within a specific time and context (Hennink et al., 2020).

Additionally, qualitative research is a valuable methodology to delve into the nuanced and subjective aspects of human experiences, attitudes, and behaviors. It centers on collecting and analyzing non-numerical data, encompassing various forms such as text, images, and audio. This method typically unfolds through diverse data-gathering techniques, including interviews, focus groups, observational studies, and document analysis. The essence of qualitative research lies in its inductive approach, whereby researchers meticulously sift through the data to identify emergent patterns, recurring themes, and profound insights, illuminating the intricate tapestry of human phenomena (Tomaszewski et al., 2020)

Moreover, qualitative research frequently addresses unstructured inquiries that probe intricate phenomena like societal conventions, cultural rituals, or individual narratives. Unlike its quantitative counterpart, the primary objective of qualitative research is not hypothesis testing or measurement but rather the cultivation of profound comprehension regarding a specific phenomenon or societal setting. It aims to produce theories or revelations that enrich subsequent research endeavors or practical applications. This method finds widespread application in disciplines such as anthropology, sociology, psychology, education, and healthcare. It contrasts quantitative research, which employs numerical data and statistical analysis to test hypotheses and quantify relationships among variables (Castell et al., 2022).

On the other hand, the phenomenological approach, which guides phenomenological inquiry, delves into the essence of human experience, aiming to understand the question, "What is the nature of this experience?" As a framework for contemplating life experiences, phenomenology primarily focuses on interpreting the significance inherent in these experiences. Consequently, phenomenological research is dedicated to investigating the essence of human existence within the world. It characterizes the phenomenological research method as an "action-sensitive understanding," initiating and concluding within the practical actions of everyday life and culminating in informed responses (Van Manen, 2023).

Likewise, phenomenological research commonly entails collecting data through interviews or comparable investigative methods, followed by a meticulous analysis to unearth recurring themes, intricate patterns, and underlying structures within the experiences under scrutiny. The overarching objective is to craft a comprehensive and intricate portrayal of the experience in focus, delving into its profound significance for the individuals who undergo it (Neubauer et al., 2019).

Similarly, phenomenology is a qualitative research approach identifying common attributes within a group's collective life encounters.

This method enabled the extraction of the inherent significance of the event, situation, or experience, fostering a more profound comprehension of the phenomenon. In the context of our study, this methodology will be employed to uncover the difficulties faced by stakeholders in school-based management. Throughout this research, the collected data will be subjected to thematic analysis, forming an integral part of the research process (Iser, 2022).

Participants

The study was conducted at General Santos City National Secondary School of Arts and Trades. The participant stakeholders were members of School-Based Management. The respondents were in school management for one year or more in the different departments of General Santos City National Secondary School of Arts and Trades.

The researcher included a total of nine (9) participants in the study, four (4) participants for Focus Group Discussion and five (5) participants for In-depth Interview (IDI). The researcher selected a focal person from each SBM stakeholder in the General Santos City National Secondary School of Arts and Trades (GSCNSSAT) Division of General Santos City school year 2017-2018. Said groups comprised the principal of the school, the elected school governing body, the SBM coordinator, elected parents of the school, students of the school (nominated by the students), barangay local government officials (Barangay Kagawad-committed on education), alums, academe (retired), and teachers.

Participants in the study were eligible for inclusion after meeting the following criteria that is, they were all General Santos City National Secondary School of Arts and Trades stakeholders. Stakeholders included students, teachers, parents, administrators, and others directly involved with or affected by the school's operations and activities. Additionally, all participants were from the same locale, ensuring a cohesive and contextually relevant sample. They were selected using the same selection criteria and methodology as the key informants, which involved a careful and systematic process to ensure representativeness and relevance to the study's objectives. This rigorous selection process helped to gather comprehensive and diverse insights, enhancing the depth and reliability of the research findings.

This study's scope was limited to the stakeholders of General Santos City National Secondary School of Arts and Trades. Participants not involved in such a program were excluded from the study. By focusing on stakeholders, this study aimed to gain a deeper understanding of the experiences, insights, and challenges stakeholders face in implementing School-Based Management.

Throughout the study, participants were told of their freedom to leave at any time without facing any repercussions. It ensured that participants knew their rights and could quickly stop participating if it made them uncomfortable or unwilling. They were not required to state their reason for withdrawal.

Data Collection

Qualitative research interviews were conducted to know the world from the subjects' point of view, unfolding the meaning of people's experiences and uncovering their lived world prior to scientific explanations. Further, qualitative research interviews unfolded as interviewers asked questions of the interviewees to gather subjective information about a particular topic or experience (McGrath et al., 2019)

I assumed a central role as the primary data collector in this qualitative research. Regardless of my academic background or inclination to classify data as quantitative or qualitative, I recognized the importance of meticulous data collection to uphold the research's integrity. I carefully selected appropriate data collection tools, whether pre-existing, adapted, or newly created, and ensured the availability of clear, precise instructions for their proper utilization. This rigorous approach significantly reduced the potential for errors during the data-gathering process.

Before commencing the study, I sought approval from the Ethics Research Committee (ERC) to ensure that the research adhered to ethical standards. Once the committee sanctioned the study, I, as the researcher, secured permission from the Dean and the Schools Division Superintendent of General Santos City to conduct the research. Upon receiving the necessary authorizations, I contacted individuals willing to participate in the study, providing them with an Informed Consent Form. It was imperative that participants comprehended the nature of the study and willingly consented to take part. After obtaining their consent, I conducted interviews to collect the requisite data for the study.

I ensured proper and ethical conduct of my research by adhering to these essential procedures. The initial phase involved interviewing the first five participants using In-depth Interviews (IDI), while the remaining four were engaged in Focus Group Discussions (FGD). Data was acquired during these participant interactions, with the research employing instruments such as interview guides, digital voice recorders, typed transcripts, field notes, and other relevant materials. Data encompassing the challenges faced by ALS learners, their coping strategies, and reflective insights were gathered after the interviews.

Transcription and data analysis were indispensable in ensuring the research's reliability. Transcription constituted the initial data analysis stage, involving and meticulously examining the data through repeated, attentive listening and observation. This familiarity with the data and a focus on what was present instead of preconceived notions facilitated the emergence of realizations and insights during the analysis process.

Data Analysis

Thematic analysis was employed in this research after collecting participants' responses. Thematic analysis was a qualitative data analysis method involving a comprehensive review of data sets, such as transcripts from in-depth interviews or focus groups, to identify recurring patterns of meaning. This method is typically used to describe texts, such as interview transcripts. My approach involved carefully examining the data to uncover recurring themes—topics, concepts, and patterns of meaning.

Thematic analysis can be executed in various ways. However, the most widely adopted method comprises six steps: familiarization, coding, theme generation, theme review, definition and labeling, and report writing. This method draws from psychological research and is versatile and applicable to various studies (Braun & Clarke, 2021).

This approach was employed to gain insights into people's perspectives, opinions, knowledge, experiences, and values. I thoroughly scrutinized the data to identify common themes among the various concepts and recurring patterns. The resulting themes, derived with the assistance of a data analyst, helped me construct a description of the research field's collected data and make informed decisions, particularly in addressing the research questions.

Several methods were utilized to analyze the data. Data Reduction was the initial step in qualitative data analysis, involving the summarization, selection of essential elements, prioritization of significant aspects, and identification of themes and patterns. The next step was Data Presentation, which involved organizing data in a concise, structured format to draw conclusions and take action (Kiger & Varpio, 2020). This step was based on formulating the research challenges during the data reduction process.

Drawing and Verifying Conclusions constituted the third step in qualitative data analysis. The qualitative analysis commenced immediately after data collection, identifying regularities, patterns, explanations, alternative configurations, causal processes, and assertions (Kiger & Varpio, 2020). Additionally, this study employed Colaizzi's data analysis framework for descriptive analysis.

Colaizzi's phenomenological data analysis process involves a distinctive seven-step process that ensures rigorous analysis while staying closely aligned with the data. The outcome is a concise yet comprehensive description of the studied phenomenon, validated by the participants who contributed to it. This method relies on rich first-person accounts of experiences, which may be obtained through various means, including face-to-face interviews, written narratives, blogs, research diaries, and online interviews.

The first step was Familiarization, wherein the researcher became acquainted with the data by thoroughly reviewing all participant accounts multiple times. The second step, Identifying Significant Statements, involved identifying all statements in the accounts directly relevant to the investigated phenomenon. The third step, Formulating Meanings, required the researcher to discern meanings about the phenomenon emerging from carefully considering the significant statements while striving to bracket preconceived notions and remain close to the experienced phenomenon.

The fourth step, Clustering Themes, entailed grouping the identified meanings into common themes in all accounts, emphasizing avoiding the influence of existing theories. The fifth step, Developing an Exhaustive Description, involved composing a comprehensive description of the phenomenon, incorporating all the themes generated in step four.

The sixth step, producing the fundamental structure, condenses the exhaustive description into a succinct assertion that captures the essential aspects of the phenomenon's structure. Lastly, in the seventh step, Seeking Verification of the Fundamental Structure, the researcher presented the fundamental structure statement to all participants (or a subset in more extensive studies) to ascertain whether it accurately represented their experiences. Based on this feedback, the researcher could revise earlier steps.

Ethical Considerations

For this quantitative study, a critical ethical factor had specific ramifications. These problems and worries mainly result from the approach used in this study. The ethical considerations in this research concerned the correct conduct of the study, confidentiality, and anonymity. The RMMC Ethics and Review Committee's requirements for ethical consideration were adhered to in this study, especially when it came to the population and data, including but not limited to:

Voluntary Participation. The participants were allowed to participate without the intention of consequences, payback, or loss of benefits. Therefore, the participant's rights to contribute to the body of knowledge were carefully considered and anticipated when the study's objective and advantages were explained to the participant. The subjects in this study were not coerced into taking part. Individuals who become uncomfortable while doing the survey can end their participation.

Privacy and confidentiality. Participants' privacy rights shall not be violated without their informed agreement under the current Data Privacy Act of 2012, which safeguards this fundamental human right. Allowing respondents to omit their names from the survey questionnaire is one technique to maintain privacy and confidentiality in this quantitative study. In addition, confidentiality and privacy were preserved by withholding the informants' personal information, such as their age, gender, occupation, and health conditions. As a result, physical interview material was preserved in a closed filing cabinet. In contrast, digital interview data was housed in a safe, encrypted database only accessed by authorized individuals. Participants were given unique codes to help anonymize all data. Physical papers would be shredded, and digital data erased using data-wiping software after the study is finished and the necessary retention

time has passed. Data would only be kept for as long as required for legal compliance and research needs, protecting participant privacy and confidentiality throughout the data gathering and disposal process.

Informed consent process. Given the limitations of the investigation, the potential research volunteers were adequately informed about the study's goals, procedures, and advantages. The participants' affirmative response demonstrated that the request for their involvement was voluntary. The fundamental details that participants needed to be aware of regarding the survey's methodology were written in writing. The informed consent form required respondents to sign to indicate that they freely chose to participate in the study. There was no need to obtain parental permission because the responders were consenting adults. The participants' identities were not listed on the survey form, and their responses were kept private. The participants knew they could withdraw from participating in the study at any time.

Furthermore, any data the researcher gathered were protected, and releasing any information would follow a strict informed consent process. The participants could control their personal information to lessen their fear that the data or information would be used in any other unintended manner.

Recruitment. The participants were informed of why they had become part of the study. For the participants to understand what the study was about, the researcher explained its purpose so that they could further infer from it and view the study's essence. In addition to the letter, the researcher explained the purpose of the study and its importance. Moreover, participants in the study were eligible if they were stakeholders of General Santos City National Secondary School of Arts and Trades, selected from the same locale and in the same manner as key informants. The study was limited to these stakeholders, excluding those not involved in the program, to understand better their experiences, insights, and challenges in implementing School-Based Management.

Risks. If the benefit-risk ratio is acceptable and positive, research will be done. This study's need to protect the participants from significant harm was equally essential. The study prioritized the welfare of the respondents. Furthermore, the respondents were not harmed since their identity was confidential. Their security and safety were of the utmost concern. As the researcher, I ensured that the respondents were physically, emotionally, and socially ready. The researcher answers the research questionnaire and confirmed that the respondents did not feel discomfort or awkwardness.

Benefits. The Department of Education could use the data-driven insights from this study to assist in implementing School-Based Management (SBM) in public schools and to direct administrators in developing efficient action plans. It sought to raise standards of instruction, give school administrators more authority, and promote openness and accountability. The research, which involved a range of stakeholders such as parents and community members, aimed to enhance community involvement and customize interventions to address particular educational needs. Professional development would help educators and administrators become more skilled, improving student outcomes and school administration. The study can ultimately help students with a better learning environment, excellent teaching quality, and enhanced academic performance, providing a more responsive and effective education system. It does this by maximizing resources and guiding policy creation.

Plagiarism. There was no hint or proof that the study had misinterpreted someone else's work. The study was subjected to plagiarism detectors like Grammarly or Turnitin software. As a researcher, I need to have positive character and integrity, which are associated with moral virtues and values. The researcher needs to be more knowledgeable about plagiarism to produce a respectable research report.

Fabrication. The report did not hint or provide evidence that the work had been intentionally misinterpreted. There was no fabrication of data or findings or deliberate presentation of incorrect conclusions. The investigator utilized and incorporated information-related theories along with additional inferential notions.

Falsification. The study did not purposefully misrepresent the work to fit a model or theoretical expectation and had no evidence of overclaiming or exaggeration. Additionally, this research did not manipulate data in any way, including but not limited to making claims, omitting crucial information, or using supplies, equipment, or techniques in a way that could deceive others.

Conflict of Interest (COI). There was no indication of a conflict of interest in the study, like disclosure of COI or circumstances where professional judgment on the principal appeal is required. It is similar to the monetary academic advantages or recognitions and tends to influence participants' welfare or the research's validity. In addition, the researcher, who had no authority or control over the respondents, forced them to participate in the survey.

Deceit. The study did not indicate that the participants were misled about any potential risk. The rights of the participants must be humongous protected in any investigation, particularly those that involve them completing higher education; hence, reasonable and fair standards must be followed.

Permission from Organization/Location. The researcher of this study followed protocols. After the panelists, adviser, and RMMCERC committee approved, the researcher formally requested permission from the superintendents of the school divisions to perform the study. After this, the researcher wrote a formal letter addressed to the district supervisor and the principal of the study's participating schools, along with a statement from the division superintendent of the school endorsing the school. The public elementary school teachers who were part of the study were oriented before administering the survey questionnaire.

Authorship. I am currently enrolled in the RMMC Graduate School. I tackled a series of revisions for my thesis based on the suggestions and recommendations made by my adviser, who guided me throughout the completion of this paper. The refinement of the paper had been made possible through the guidance of my adviser.

Results

This section presents rich information provided by participants to explore the phenomenon under study. It often involves a detailed account of how the data was gathered, organized, and analyzed the themes that emerged.

Description of Participants

There were nine informants of this study. All the key informants were stakeholders of General Santos City National Secondary School of Arts and Trades stakeholders. All nine participants were either former or present stakeholders of the said school. They were selected as participants in the study because of their experiences, which determined their understanding of school-based management implementation leadership and governance at General Santos City National Secondary School of Arts and Trades.

Principal Smith, 46, the head administrator of the school brought years of experience to the table. With a deep commitment to the school's mission and values, Principal Smith played a pivotal role in overseeing all aspects of school management.

Council Chair Garcia, 37 years old, a dedicated member of the elected School Governing Council, served as the council's chairperson. Garcia provided tremendous expertise and leadership to the position and is strongly dedicated to improving education. This helped to ensure that the council's activities aligned with the needs and goals of the school community. The council, led by Garcia, has effectively executed multiple initiatives to improve student performance and cultivate a cooperative atmosphere between educators, guardians, and community members. Garcia's commitment to accountability and openness has been crucial in fostering trust and promoting constructive changes in the educational system.

Coordinator Rodriguez, 35, served as the School-Based Management (SBM) Coordinator, pivotal in assisting the school in implementing SBM policy. Thanks to his extensive experience and solid grasp of educational management principles, Rodriguez ensured that SBM practices were successfully incorporated into the school's structure. The school's resource distribution, community involvement, and decision-making procedures have all significantly improved under Rodriguez's direction.

Parent Martinez, 42, is a passionate advocate for parental involvement in the school community. Martinez deeply understood the importance of parental engagement in fostering student success and actively promoted initiatives to increase parental participation in school activities and decision-making processes.

Student Lee, aged 16, held the esteemed position of representing the student body's interests within the school community. Nominated by peers for their exemplary leadership qualities and dedication to student welfare, Lee served as a voice for fellow students in decision-making processes.

Sir Kagawad, aged 41, commands respect as a local government official overseeing education-related affairs within the barangay (local community). Due to his extensive knowledge and strong dedication to the local community's well-being, Sir Kagawad was essential in ensuring that educational programs are carried out successfully and that resources are distributed appropriately.

Sarah, 20, is a proud alumna of the school, having graduated several years ago. She is deeply connected to and appreciative of her alma institution, and she actively supports several school initiatives and events.

Sir Anderson, aged 63, is a retired academician with a distinguished career in education. Even in retirement, Sir Anderson made a significant impact on the subject of education thanks to his extensive knowledge and expertise gained over the years. Sir Anderson shapes the future generation of educational leaders by serving as a mentor and counselor to aspirant educators, imparting priceless knowledge and insight.

Mrs. Teach, 33 years old, is a dedicated and passionate teacher within the school. With a commitment to nurturing young minds and fostering a positive learning environment, she plays a crucial role in shaping her students' educational experiences.

Categorization of Data

This part meticulously categorizes data to offer a comprehensive examination of key themes. It delves into the myriad challenges faced, the adaptive coping mechanisms employed, and the reflective insights from stakeholders in their pursuit of implementing SBM.

3.1. Challenges of Stakeholders in the Implementation of School-Based Management (SBM) Leadership and Governance

Table 1 presents the challenges of stakeholders in implementing school-based management (SBM) and depicts the selection criteria as identified. Five challenges were discussed in this study. The table describes the essential themes of stakeholders' challenges in implementing School-Based Management (SBM). Moreover, core ideas were presented based on the responses of participants.

Lack of Support in SBM Implementation. This theme encompasses stakeholders' challenges in implementing School-Based Management (SBM). These challenges include insufficient funding, decision-making conflicts, time constraints, and difficulties

engaging parents and the community.

Participants highlighted critical challenges within the School-Based Management (SBM) framework. These include ensuring responsible financial management, balancing teaching responsibilities with SBM duties, and addressing conflicting opinions among stakeholders.

"Bilang isang SBM officer, isa sa mga hamon ay ang pagiging responsable sa financial management. Kailangan naming siguruhin na ang bawat piso ay nauukit sa tamang proyekto at hindi nasasayang. Ang pressure ay mataas, lalo na't ito ay para sa kinabukasan ng mga mag-aaral." (IDM-Participant 1, lines 343-346).

One of the challenges of being an SBM officer is being responsible for financial management. We must ensure that every peso is allocated to the right project and not wasted. The pressure is high, especially since it is for the student's future.

"Ako ay isang guro at SBM coordinator. Ang challenge para sa akin ay ang pagba-balance ng aking teaching responsibilities at SBM duties. Madalas, nagiging overloaded kami sa trabaho, ngunit kailangan itong magkasamang gawin para sa overall improvement ng paaralan." (IDM-Participant 2, lines 440-443).

I am a teacher and an SBM coordinator. My challenge is balancing my teaching responsibilities and SBM duties. Often, we become overloaded with work, but it needs to be done together for the school's overall improvement.

Participants identified the need for sufficient funding for school projects, the difficulty of reaching consensus on decisions, the time constraints teachers face in allocating time for SBM, and the struggle to ensure active participation from parents and the community.

"Sa tingin ko, isa sa mga malalaking hamon sa SBM ay ang kakulangan ng sapat na pondo o budget para sa mga proyekto ng paaralan. May mga pagkakataon na hindi natin magawa ang mga plano natin dahil sa limitadong resources. Isa rin sa mga kinakaharap natin ay ang pagkakaroon ng consensus sa mga desisyon sa SBM. Hindi palaging magkakasundo ang lahat ng stakeholders sa kung paano gastusin ang pondo o alin ang mga proyekto ang unahin. Kaya't nagkakaroon ng delays at pagkakaroon ng tensyon sa grupo." (FGD-Participant 1, lines 4-10).

One of the significant challenges in SBM is the need for sufficient funding or budget for school projects. We sometimes need more resources to carry out our plans. Another challenge we face is reaching a consensus on decisions within SBM. Not all stakeholders always agree on how to allocate the funds or prioritize projects, which leads to delays and tension within the group.

"Tama ka d'yan. Isa pa, ang pagkakaroon ng sapat na oras upang maglaan para sa SBM ay isa rin sa mga hamon. Bilang mga guro, may mga pagkakataon na nagiging sobra-sobra ang trabaho namin, at ito'y nangangahulugang mas mahirap maglaan ng oras para sa SBM. Madalas, marami sa amin ay nagkakaroon ng stress sa pagtutugma ng aming SBM responsibilities sa aming regular na trabaho." (FGD-Participant 2, lines 11-16).

You are right about that. Another challenge is having enough time to allocate to SBM. As teachers, there are times when our workload becomes overwhelming, making it harder to find time for SBM. Many of us experience stress balancing our SBM responsibilities with our regular work.

Roles and Involvement in SBM Leadership. This theme focuses on the roles and involvement of participants in SBM leadership and governance within their schools or institutions. It sheds light on the responsibilities, challenges, and motivations of those actively participating in SBM.

Participants highlighted critical challenges within the School-Based Management (SBM) framework. These include ensuring responsible financial management, balancing teaching responsibilities with SBM duties, and addressing conflicting opinions among stakeholders.

"Ako ay kasalukuyang may limang taon nang sangkot sa SBM. Ang motibasyon ko ay ang pag-asa na mas mapabuti ang mga pasilidad at oportunidad para sa aming mga mag-aaral. Gusto kong maging bahagi ng pagbabago." (IDM-Participant 1, lines 349-352).

I have been involved in SBM for five years now. I hope to improve the facilities and opportunities for our students, and I want to be a part of the change.

"Nagsimula akong maging kasali sa SBM sa loob ng tatlong taon. Ang inspirasyon ko ay ang mga estudyante. Nais kong magkaroon sila ng mas magandang learning environment kaya't nag-volunteer akong maging coordinator." (IDM-Participant 2, lines 446-449).

I started being involved in SBM three years ago. My inspiration is the students. I want them to have a better learning environment, so I volunteered as a coordinator.

"Nasa SBM ako ng mahigit sa anim na taon. Ako'y motivated ng aking commitment sa educational leadership. Alam kong may magagawa akong pagbabago sa aming paaralan." (IDM-Participant 5, lines 703-705).

I have been in SBM for over six years. I am motivated by my commitment to educational leadership. I can make a difference in our school.

Participants also outlined challenges such as financial management, which requires careful resource allocation to benefit students, and balancing teaching duties with SBM responsibilities. Moreover, establishing effective communication and coordination among stakeholders proves challenging, often leading to disagreements on decisions and plans. Additionally, budgetary constraints present hurdles in funding essential school needs, demanding collaborative efforts and clear spending plans.

"Sa aking tungkulin sa SBM leadership at governance, isa sa mga malalaking hamon ay ang pangangailangan para sa regular na pag-aaral at pagsusuri ng mga financial reports at budget ng paaralan. Dahil dito, kinakailangan namin ng sapat na oras at pagsisikap upang siguruhing ang mga gastusin ay naaayon sa mga proyekto at pangangailangan ng mga mag-aaral. Isa pa, ang pagkakaroon ng ugnayan at koordinasyon sa pagitan ng mga guro, magulang, at iba pang stakeholders ay hindi palaging madaling gawin. May mga pagkakataon na hindi magkakasundo sa mga desisyon o mga plano, at kailangan naming maghanap ng paraan para maayos ang mga ito. Hindi rin namin maiiwasan ang kakulangan ng budget para sa mga kinakailangang gawin sa paaralan. Madalas naming nararanasan ang kakulangan sa pondo para sa mga basic na pangangailangan tulad ng kagamitan, maintenance, at mga pampaganda ng paaralan. Bilang isang guro, kinakailangan namin magtaguyod ng malasakit at dedikasyon sa SBM upang masiguro ang maayos na pamamahala ng paaralan. Ito ay nagiging pagsubok, lalo na kung may mga pagkakataon na nadadala kami ng stress at pressure dahil sa mga ito." (FGD-Participant 1, lines 25-40).

In my role in SBM leadership and governance, one of the significant challenges is the need for regular study and analysis of the school's financial reports and budget. Because of this, we require sufficient time and effort to ensure that expenses align with the projects and students' needs. Another challenge is establishing connections and coordination among teachers, parents, and other stakeholders, which can be challenging. Sometimes, we do not agree on decisions or plans, and we need to find ways to resolve these issues. Budgetary constraints for essential school needs such as supplies, maintenance, and beautification are also standard. Teachers must advocate for dedication and commitment to SBM to ensure adequate school management. It can be challenging, especially when stress and pressure come into play.

"Bilang miyembro ng SBM leadership, ang isa sa mga hamon sa aking tungkulin ay ang pagbalanse ng oras. Sa isang panig, kinakailangan kong magtutok sa mga pangangailangan ng SBM, tulad ng pagbuo ng proyekto at pag-audit ng gastusin. Sa kabilang banda, ako ay isang guro, kaya't may mga oras din akong inuukit para sa pagtuturo at paggabay sa mga mag-aaral. Mahirap ito gawin nang sabay-sabay, at kailangan kong ma-manage nang mabuti ang aking oras. Isa pa, ang pagsasanib-puwersa ng iba't-ibang pananaw at interes ng mga stakeholders ay hindi palaging madali. Madalas may pagtatalo o hindi pagkakasunduan sa mga desisyon, at kinakailangan naming magkaruon ng proseso para ma-address ito. Sa totoo lang, minsan ay napapagod ako, lalo na kapag maraming nangyayaring pulong at pag-audit. Pero inuukit ko sa aking isipan na ang SBM ay para sa kapakanan ng mga mag-aaral, kaya't ito ay isang hamon na handa kong harapin." (FGD-Participant 2, lines 41-53).

As a member of SBM leadership, one of the challenges in my role is time management. On the one hand, I need to focus on SBM requirements like project development and budget audits. On the other hand, I am a teacher, so I also have hours allocated for teaching and guiding students. Balancing these tasks can be difficult, and I must manage my time effectively. Additionally, reconciling the different perspectives and interests of stakeholders can be challenging. There are often disagreements or need for more consensus on decisions, and we need to establish processes to address these issues. There are times when I get tired, especially when there are many meetings and audits. However, I remind myself that SBM is for the benefit of the students, so it is a challenge I am willing to face.

Miscommunication. This theme explores how SBM has influenced the overall dynamics of the school or institution, both positively and less favorably. It highlights changes in collaboration, educational focus, project implementation, and potential challenges like conflicts and delays.

Participants highlighted several challenges associated with implementing School-Based Management (SBM) in their schools. Despite the positive outcomes, conflicts arise over the allocation of funds, reflecting differing priorities and interests among stakeholders. Additionally, bureaucratic decision-making processes hinder progress despite increased community unity and parental involvement. Furthermore, debates on educational strategies sometimes devolve into ego battles, undermining accountability and cooperation.

"Napagtagumpayan namin ang pag-improve ng mga classroom facilities at learning resources. Mas naging komportable ang aming mga mag-aaral at mas nagkaroon sila ng access sa mga quality materials para sa kanilang edukasyon." (IDM-Participant 1, lines 366-369).

We are successful in improving the classroom facilities and learning resources. Our students are significantly more comfortable, and they can have access to quality materials in their education.

"Nakita kong mas nagkaroon ng voice ang mga magulang at teachers sa mga school policies. Pero, sa negatibong aspeto, minsan may pagkakaiba-iba ng opinion sa allocation ng funds na nagdudulot ng conflict." (IDM-Participant 2, lines 470-472).

Parents and teachers have gained a stronger voice in school policies. However, on the negative side, there are times when differing opinions on fund allocation lead to conflicts.

"Napansin ko na mas naging proactive ang mga magulang sa school affairs, at naging mas magkakasundo ang community. Ngunit, may mga pagkakataon na nagiging bureaucratic ang proseso ng decision-making." (IDM-Participant 3, lines 555-557).

I noticed that parents have become more proactive in school affairs, and the community has become more united. However, there are times when the decision-making process becomes bureaucratic.

Participants also identified challenges such as delays in decision-making due to debates, conflicts within SBM teams, inconsistent parental attendance at meetings, and the need for effective communication.

"Napansin namin na ang SBM ay nagdala ng mas malalim na ugnayan sa pagitan ng mga guro, magulang, at iba pang stakeholders. Ito ay nagpositibo sa pagtutulongan at pag-aambag ng bawat isa sa pag-unlad ng paaralan. Ngunit, minsan, nagkakaroon ito ng delays sa decision-making dahil sa debate at hindi pagkakasundo." (FGD-Participant 1, lines 153-159).

SBM has brought a more profound connection among teachers, parents, and other stakeholders. It has positively impacted collaboration and contributions from each party in school development. However, sometimes, it delays decision-making due to debates and disagreements.

"Napansin namin na mas naging proactive ang aming paaralan sa pag-implement ng mga educational innovations. Ito ay nagpapabuti sa learning experience ng mga mag-aaral. Subalit, kinakailangan naming siguruhing maayos ang communication para maiwasan ang mga delays sa mga proyekto." (FGD-Participant 4, lines 168-171).

Due to SBM, we've noticed that our school has become more proactive in implementing educational innovations. This improves the learning experience for students. However, we need to ensure effective communication to avoid project delays.

Initial Expectations About SBM. Participants reflected on their initial expectations when SBM was introduced. They anticipated increased empowerment, transparency in budget management, and more vital parental involvement in their children's education.

Initially hopeful for addressing school governance challenges, SBM implementation faced obstacles. Challenges included stakeholder consensus struggles, conflicts over fund allocation leading to delays, balancing SBM with teaching duties, and ensuring active parental participation.

"Noong una, inaasahan ko na ang SBM ay magdadala ng mas malalim na financial transparency at efficient resource allocation sa paaralan. Naisip ko rin na mas makakapag-focus tayo sa mga projects na tunay na makakatulong sa mga mag-aaral." (IDM-Participant 1, lines 355-358).

At first, I expected that SBM would bring deeper financial transparency and efficient resource allocation to the school. We can focus on activities that will help students.

"Sa simula, ini-expect ko na ang SBM ay magbibigay ng boses sa mga magulang at stakeholders. Naisip kong ito ay magdadala ng mas magandang kooperasyon sa pagitan ng paaralan at community para sa kapakanan ng mga mag-aaral." (IDM-Participant 3, lines 538-541).

Initially, I expected SBM to give parents and stakeholders a voice. I also expected it to bring about better cooperation between the school and the community, which would benefit the students.

"Nang unang pumasok ang SBM sa paaralan, ini-expect ko na ito ay magdadala ng mas malalim na mga discussion sa educational policies at strategies. Naisip ko rin na magkakaroon tayo ng mas systematic na planning at implementation ng projects." (IDM-Participant 4, lines 623-626).

When SBM first entered the school, I expected it to bring more in-depth discussions on educational policies and strategies. We would also have a more systematic planning and implementation of projects.

Participants anticipated increased empowerment for teachers and stakeholders in decision-making, expecting more precise voices in educational matters. However, while hoping for faster school development and enhanced transparency in budget management, they faced challenges in achieving consensus and balancing SBM responsibilities with teaching duties.

"Noong una kong narinig ang SBM, inaasahan kong ito ay magdadala ng mas malawak na kapangyarihan para sa mga guro at stakeholders sa pagdedesiyon. Inaasahan kong magkakaroon tayo ng mas malinaw na boses sa mga usaping pang-edukasyon sa paaralan." (FGD-Participant 1, lines 97-100).

When I first heard about SBM, I expected it to bring more empowerment for teachers and stakeholders in decision-making. I anticipated we would have a more unmistakable voice in educational matters within the school.

"Ako ay umaasa na ang SBM ay magbukas ng mga pintuan para sa mas mabilis na pag-unlad ng paaralan. Inaasahan kong mas magiging transparent ang pamamahala ng pondo at mas maraming oportunidad para sa mga mag-aaral." (FGD-Participant 2, lines 101-104).

I hope that SBM will open doors for faster school development. Budget management will become more transparent, and students will have more opportunities.

"Mayroon kaming mga disagreements sa prioritization ng projects. Ang ginagawa namin ay nagko-conduct ng debate, pero hindi ito nauuwi sa personal na conflicts. Kinakailangan namin mag-vote para mag-decide at respetuhin ang resulta." (FGD-Participant 2, lines 198-201).

We have disagreements regarding project prioritization. We conduct debates, but they do not escalate into personal conflicts. We need to vote to make decisions and respect the outcome.

"Naranasan namin ang conflicts sa pagpapalano ng mga activities. Kami ay nagpapalitan ng mga opinyon, at kung kinakailangan, naghahanap kami ng compromise para ma-address ang mga issues. Importante na magkaruon ng open communication para ma-solve ang mga ito." (FGD-Participant 3, lines 202-205).

We have experienced conflicts in planning activities. We exchange opinions, and if necessary, we look for compromises to address the issues. Open communication is essential to resolving these matters.

Balancing SBM Responsibilities with Other Obligations. Participants highlighted the importance of time management, prioritization, and teamwork to balance their SBM responsibilities with teaching, administrative tasks, and personal life.

Participants prioritized various responsibilities, including teaching duties, family commitments, personal studies, and contributions to SBM projects. They emphasized the importance of balancing these roles while highlighting the significance of effective time management and coordination in fulfilling their duties within the school and the broader community.

"Inuuna ko ang mga gawain sa pagtuturo, at pagkatapos nito, doon ko itinutuon ang mga trabaho sa ilalim ng SBM. Mahalaga ang tamang oras para sa bawat responsibilidad, pati na rin ang personal na buhay." (IDM-Participant 1, lines 393-395).

I prioritize my teaching duties and then focus on tasks under SBM. Allocating the right amount of time for each responsibility and my personal life is essential.

"Inuuna ko ang aking pag-aaral, ngunit pinahahalagahan ko ang mga proyekto ng SBM. Nagbibigay ako ng aking opinyon para sa ikabubuti ng paaralan." (IDM-Participant 3, lines 573-575).

I prioritize my studies, but I also value the SBM projects. I contribute my opinions to improve the school.

Participants underscored the importance of effective time management and work-life balance. They highlighted strategies such as creating schedules, using time management tools, prioritizing tasks, and collaborating within SBM teams. Additionally, they emphasized the need for designated time for personal activities and self-care to ensure well-being amidst professional responsibilities.

"Para sa akin, mahalaga ang pagtutok sa time management. Gumagawa ako ng schedule at inuuna ang mga deadlines sa SBM at sa pagtuturo. Sa personal life, kinakailangan ng work-life balance, kaya't mayroon akong allotted time para sa pamilya at sarili." (FGD-Participant 1, lines 213-216).

Focusing on time management is crucial for me. I create a schedule and prioritize deadlines for both SBM and teaching responsibilities. Maintaining a work-life balance is essential in my personal life, so I allocate specific time for my family and myself.

"Kinakailangan ng prioritization. Sa pagtuturo, inuuna ko ang mga importanteng lessons, at ganun din sa SBM responsibilities. Kapag may mga overlapping commitments, nilalata ko ang mga plano para masunod ang lahat ng dapat gawin." (FGD-Participant 3, lines 221-225).

"Prioritization is necessary. I prioritize essential lessons in teaching and do the same with my SBM responsibilities. I plan to ensure that everything gets done when there are overlapping commitments.

Innovative Approaches to Improve SBM Processes. Participants described innovative approaches to enhancing SBM processes, such as using technology for financial tracking, organizing interactive workshops and storytelling sessions, and implementing online collaboration platforms.

Participants highlighted innovative approaches to school management, including the use of technology for financial management, the establishment of online portals for parental engagement, and the implementation of teacher mentoring programs.

"Isa sa mga innovative approaches na ginagamit namin ay ang paggamit ng technology sa financial management. Nag-implement kami ng digital budgeting system na nagpapabilis ng transaksyon at nagbibigay ng real-time updates." (IDM-Participant 1, lines 399-402).

One of our innovative approaches is employing technology for financial management. We implemented a digital budgeting system that expedites transactions and provides real-time updates.

"Nagtayo kami ng online portal para sa parental engagement. Dito, ang mga magulang ay makakakuha ng regular updates tungkol sa kanilang mga anak at sa mga school activities." (IDM-Participant 2, lines 494-496).

We established an online portal for parental engagement. Here, parents can receive regular updates about their children and school

activities.

"Kami ay nag-develop ng teacher mentoring program kung saan ang mga seasoned teachers ay nagme-mentor sa mga bagong guro. Ito ay nagpapalakas ng teacher development at retention." (IDM-Participant 4, lines 665-667).

We developed a teacher mentoring program where seasoned teachers mentor new educators. It strengthens teacher development and retention.

Participants also highlighted innovative strategies within the SBM framework, including technology integration for financial tracking, fostering parental involvement through interactive conferences, utilizing storytelling to communicate plans effectively, and implementing online collaboration platforms for swift communication.

"Sa SBM, naging innovative kami sa paggamit ng technology para sa financial tracking. Gumawa kami ng digital system na mas pinadali ang pag-monitor ng budget at expenses. Ito ay nakakatulong sa aming mas mahusay na financial management." (FGD-Participant 1, lines 232-235).

At SBM, we have become innovative in using technology for financial tracking. We developed a digital system that simplified budget and expense monitoring, helping us achieve better financial management.

"Sa SBM meetings, ginagamit namin ang storytelling approach para mas maintindihan ng mga stakeholders ang mga plano. Ibinabahagi namin ang mga success stories ng mga mag-aaral na na-impact ng SBM projects, at ito ay nagiging inspirasyon sa aming lahat." (FGD-Participant 3, lines 240-243).

In SBM meetings, we use storytelling to help stakeholders better understand our plans. We share success stories of students whose SBM projects have impacted them, which inspires us all.

"Upang mas mapabilis ang communication sa SBM team, nag-set kami ng online collaboration platform kung saan pwede naming i-share ang updates at discussions. Ito ay nagpapabilis ng decision-making at pag-follow up ng mga actions." (FGD-Participant 4, lines 244-247).

To facilitate faster communication within the SBM team, we established an online collaboration platform to share updates and engage in discussions. It speeds up decision-making and allows us to follow up on actions more efficiently.

Seeking Support and Guidance during Challenging Times. During difficult or frustrating situations, participants sought support from various sources, including their SBM teams, mentors, successful SBM practitioners from other schools, Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs), and educational authorities like the Department of Education (DepEd).

Participants highlighted the importance of seeking support and guidance within the SBM framework during challenging times. They mentioned turning to fellow SBM leaders in other schools, their school's SBM council, designated mentorship programs, and local SBM networks for assistance.

"Ako ay nagtutungo sa aming school's SBM council para sa support at guidance. Sila ay may malalim na understanding sa challenges na kinakaharap namin." (IDM-Participant 2, lines 499-501).

I turn to our school's SBM council for support and guidance. They have a deep understanding of our challenges.

"Sa aming school, may designated mentorship program para sa SBM leaders. Kami ay nagtutulungan para sa emotional support at pag-resolve ng mga conflicts." (IDM-Participant 4, lines 670-672).

In our school, there is a designated mentorship program for SBM leaders. We collaborate to provide emotional support and resolve conflicts.

"Ako ay humahanap ng suporta sa aming SBM network sa lokal na komunidad. Kami ay nagkakaroon ng regular na meetings para pag-usapan ang mga challenges at solutions." (IDM-Participant 5, lines 751-753).

I seek support from our SBM network within the local community. We hold regular meetings to discuss challenges and solutions.

Participants also highlighted diverse avenues of support during challenging moments within the SBM framework. They emphasized turning to their SBM team for collaborative problem-solving, seeking guidance from mentors and successful practitioners, engaging with the Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) for feedback and support, and relying on the assistance of SBM coordinators and the Department of Education (DepEd).

"Sa mga challenging moments, kami ay nagtutungo sa aming SBM team para sa suporta. Nagkakaroon kami ng open discussion at brainstorming sessions para masolusyunan ang mga issues." (FDG-Participant 1, lines 250-252).

In challenging moments, we turn to our SBM team for support. We engage in open discussions and brainstorming sessions to find solutions to the issues at hand.

"Kami ay may mentor na taga-educational leadership na nagbibigay ng guidance. Nagko-consult din kami sa mga successful na SBM practitioners sa ibang schools para sa best practices." (FGD-Participant 2, lines 253-255).

We have a mentor in educational leadership who provides guidance. We also consult with successful SBM practitioners from other schools for best practices.

"Sa mga pagkakataon ng frustration, nagtutungo kami sa aming Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) para sa feedback at suporta. Kinakausap namin ang mga magulang para malaman ang kanilang concerns." (FGD-Participant 3, lines 256-258).

In times of frustration, we turn to our Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) for feedback and support. We engage with parents to understand their concerns.

Table 2. *Coping Mechanism in the Implementation of School Based Management (SBM) Leadership and Governance*

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
Importance of transparent discussions and open communication.	Confluct Resolution within the SBM Framework
Collaboration and cooperation among team members to resolve conflicts.	
Present financial data or research findings to resolve conflicts.	
Actively seek common ground and compromise to address conflicts.	
Time Management.	
Focus on small wins.	
Open communication wuithin the SBM team.	
Brainstorming sessions are held to generate ideas and analyze the pros and cons.	
Maintaining work-life balance is essential.	
Time management tools such as calendars and to-do-list to manage time between teaching and SBM responsibilities effectively.	
Collaborative approach.	Innovative Approachers to Improve SBM Processes
Prioritize essential lessons, self-care to refresh, duties and the children, and focus on their education and studies. Also, value the SBM projects.	
Coordination and communication are crucial in fulfilling responsibilities in school and the community.	
Innovative in using technology for financial tracking.	
Regular Parent-Teacher Conferences with interactive workshops.	
Storytelling approach to help stakeholders better undertand our plans.	
Established an online collaboration platform.	
Use technology for financial management.	
Online portal for parental engagement.	
Focusing on long-term goals helps	
A teacher mentoring program.	Seeking Support and Guidance during Challenging Times
SBM team for support.	
A mentor in educational leadership who provides guidance.	
Feedback and support from the Parent-Teacher Association (PTA)	
Delegate SBM coordinator who serves as mentor and adviser.	
Guidance from fellow SBM leasers in other schools.	
Turn to the school's SBM Council.	
A mentorship program for SBM leaders.	
Established a support network.	
SBM network within the local community.	

3.3. Insights of Stakeholders in the Implementation of School-Based Management (SBM) Leadership and Governance

Table 3 presents stakeholders' insights into implementing school-based management (SBM) and identifies themes that emerged. The table describes the essential themes gathered regarding stakeholders' insights in the implementation of school-based management (SBM). Moreover, core ideas were presented based on the responses of participants.

Transparency and Communication within SBM. This theme emphasized the importance of open and transparent communication within the SBM framework. Participants highlighted that transparency in financial transactions and decision-making processes is crucial for SBM's success. Clear communication ensured that stakeholders are well-informed and unified in their actions.

"Ayon sa aking karanasan, ang transparency at open communication sa lahat ng stakeholders ay pangunahing factor sa tagumpay ng SBM. Kapag lahat ay nakikilahok at nagkakaroon ng access sa impormasyon, mas nagiging maayos ang governance." (IDM-Participant 1, lines 411-414).

Transparency and open communication among all stakeholders are critical factors in the success of SBM. When everyone is involved and has access to information, governance becomes more efficient.

"Isa sa mga ways na maaari nating mapabuti ay ang pagkakaroon ng mas malinaw na mechanisms para sa mga complaints o feedback. Dapat ito ay mas ma-promote at maging transparent." (IDM-Participant 5, lines 757-759).

We can improve by having more precise mechanisms for complaints or feedback. It should be promoted more and made transparent.

"Para sa amin, transparency ang pangunahing factor. Ito ay ang pagiging bukas at malinaw sa financial transactions at decision-making. Kapag alam ng lahat ang nangyayari, mas nagiging unified ang aming actions." (FGD-Participant 1, lines 266-268).

For us, transparency is the primary factor. It involves being open and transparent in financial transactions and decision-making. When everyone knows what is happening, our actions become more unified.

"Empowerment ng stakeholders ang nakikita kong mahalaga. Kapag ang bawat isa ay nakakaramdam na sila ay may boses at may pagkakataon mag-contribute, mas nagiging effective ang SBM." (FDG-Participant 2, lines 269-271).

Empowering stakeholders is essential. When everyone feels they have a voice and an opportunity to contribute, SBM (School-Based Management) becomes more effective.

Empowerment and Collaboration. Empowering stakeholders and fostering collaboration were essential factors for the SBM's success. Participants stressed the importance of giving everyone a voice and an opportunity to contribute, which made SBM more effective. Collaboration among SBM teams, teachers, parents, and other stakeholders is emphasized to achieve success.

"Inaasam ko na sa hinaharap, mas magiging inclusive ang SBM, kasama na ang mga marginalized sectors. Gusto ko ring mas ma-sustain ang transparency at collaboration sa lahat ng aspects ng SBM." (IDM-Participant 1, lines 423-425).

In the future, I hope that SBM becomes more inclusive, including marginalized sectors. I also want transparency and collaboration to be sustained in all aspects of SBM.

"Para sa akin, dapat bigyan pansin ang mga performance metrics para mas mapanatili ang accountability sa SBM. Kailangan nating malaman kung ano ang tunay na nagwowork." (IDM-Participant 4, lines 676-678).

We should focus on performance metrics to maintain accountability in SBM. We need to know what indeed works.

"Active participation ng magulang at community ay kritikal. Kapag sila ay kasama sa proseso at engaged sa mga activities, mas maraming ideas at resources ang nagiging available." (FGD-Participant 3, lines 272-274).

The active participation of guardians and the community is critical. When they are involved in the process and engaged in activities, more ideas and resources become available.

"Sa aming experience, ang collaboration sa pagitan ng SBM team, guro, magulang, at iba pang stakeholders ay nagdadala ng tagumpay. Ito ay dahil sa bawat isa ay may natututunan at nag-aambag sa improvement ng paaralan." (FGD-Participant 4, lines 275-278).

Collaboration among the SBM team, teachers, parents, and other stakeholders brings success. Everyone learns and contributes to the improvement of the school.

Improvement of SBM. The participants collectively acknowledged the need for improvement in various aspects of SBM. These include financial literacy, stakeholder engagement, communication, monitoring and evaluation, and performance metrics.

"Sa aking tingin, ang engagement ng magulang at komunidad ay kritikal. Kapag sila ay aktibo at kasali sa mga desisyon at mga proyekto, mas naii-angat ang kalidad ng edukasyon." (IDM-Participant 3, lines 587-589).

Parent and community engagement is critical. When parents and community members are active and involved in decisions and projects, the quality of education is significantly improved.

"Para sa akin, dapat bigyang pansin ang mga performance metrics para mas mapanatili ang accountability sa SBM. Kailangan nating malaman kung ano ang tunay na nagwowork." (IDM-Participant 4, lines 676-678).

We should focus on performance metrics to maintain accountability in SBM. We need to know what indeed works.

"Para sa amin, kailangan pa namin mapalakas ang financial literacy ng mga stakeholders. Dapat silang ma-train upang mas maunawaan ang budgeting at financial reports para sa mas magandang financial management." (FGD-Participant 1, lines 282-284).

We needed to strengthen the financial literacy of our stakeholders. They should be trained to understand budgeting and financial reports, which will improve their financial management.

"Nakikita namin na importante ang mas malinaw na communication. Dapat ay ma-improve pa ang dissemination ng information tungkol sa SBM projects at activities para mas marami ang makakaalam at makakilahok." (FGD-Participant 3, lines 289-292).

We saw that clear communication was essential. The dissemination of information about SBM projects and activities should be further improved so that more people can be informed and be participative.

Table 3. *Insights of Stakeholders in the Implementation of School-Based Management (SBM) Leadership and Governance*

<i>Cluster Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Transparency is the primary factor. Open communication among all stakeholders is a crucial factor. Financial transparency. Efficient communication and data analysis. Promote more and make transparent. Active participation of parents and the community.	Transparency of Communication among SBM leaders
Collaboration among the SBM team, teachers, parents and the stakeholders. Improving parent and community engagement is crucial. Strengthen the financial literacy of our stakeholders. Deeper engagement of parents.	
SBM projects and activities should be further improved. The quality of education is significantly improved. Focus on performance metrics to maintain accountability in SBM	Improvement of SBM

Discussion

The views in every category, significant findings, and comparison of results with existing studies, limitations of the research, implications for future research, and the overall significance of the qualitative research on the lived experiences of stakeholders in the implementation of School-Based Management Leadership and Governance at General Santos City National Secondary School of Arts and Trades (GSCNSSAT) were presented in this chapter.

Challenges Experienced by Stakeholders in the Implementation of School-Based Management (SBM) Leadership and Governance. Four major themes emerged from the data collected on the challenges experienced by stakeholders in SBM: Lack of Support in SBM implementation, roles and involvement in SBM leadership, miscommunication, and initial expectations about SBM.

Lack of Support in SBM Implementation. Implementing School-Based Management (SBM) faced several significant challenges that could have hindered its success. One of the foremost issues was the need for more sufficient funding or a budget for school projects. Schools often found themselves constrained by financial limitations, making executing necessary initiatives and improvements challenging. Additionally, time management was a prevalent challenge, as teachers had to balance their teaching responsibilities with SBM duties, which could be time-consuming.

Moreover, another critical challenge lies in garnering active participation from parents and the community. Many schools struggled to involve parents effectively in school decisions and activities, and low attendance at parent meetings exacerbated this issue. Furthermore, parental support for school initiatives could be lacking, making it difficult to implement changes effectively. Financial management posed challenges, requiring schools to navigate budgetary responsibilities and accountability. Balancing teaching and SBM duties were particularly demanding, highlighting the need for better time management strategies. Encouraging other parents to become involved and stay informed was an ongoing challenge that impacted the effectiveness of SBM. Finally, while essential, the overarching goal of boosting student performance presented its unique challenges, such as curriculum development and teacher training.

This assumption parallels the study of Catam and Punzalan (2019), who reported the issue of insufficient funding or budget allocation for school projects. Researchers have highlighted how inadequate financial resources can severely hinder the successful execution of SBM initiatives. Limited budgets constrain schools, making investing in necessary improvements, resource allocation, and even staff training challenging. This funding shortfall can significantly impact the effectiveness of SBM in promoting school improvement. Time management emerges as another pervasive challenge in SBM implementation. Many studies have emphasized how educators often struggle to balance their regular teaching responsibilities with the demands of SBM.

Roles and Involvement in SBM Leadership. The statements provided a multifaceted School-Based Management (SBM) leadership and governance landscape. They highlighted the diverse roles undertaken by individuals in the context of SBM, encompassing educators, parents, and officers who shouldered various responsibilities within the framework. One recurrent challenge emerged as a time management issue, affecting SBM leaders and parents who were deeply involved in the process. Balancing their existing roles and responsibilities with SBM duties was a common struggle. For teachers, transparent communication within the SBM context was essential, underlining its significance in fostering effective collaboration.

Additionally, the duration of involvement in SBM varied widely, with some participants having served for several years while others had more recently embarked on their SBM journey. This diversity in experiences and engagement lengths enriched the perspectives brought to the table and contributed to a dynamic SBM environment. Furthermore, particular participants, such as officers, held specific leadership positions within SBM, further influencing the dynamics of governance and the challenges they faced.

This assumption parallels the study of Delgado (2019), which highlighted the financial constraints schools face in implementing SBM effectively. Inadequate funding can hinder the successful implementation of SBM, as schools may need help to allocate resources for various initiatives. Additionally, teachers and SBM leaders often need help to balance their regular teaching duties with the additional responsibilities of SBM involvement. Time constraints can impact the quality of decision-making and overall SBM effectiveness.

Miscommunication. The participants' statements illuminated the miscommunication of School-Based Management (SBM) on school dynamics and stakeholder relationships. SBM notably deepened connections among teachers, parents, and stakeholders, fostering collaboration and shared ownership. It gave schools a more precise educational direction, enhancing effectiveness by prioritizing student learning outcomes. SBM's positive influence on parental involvement and engagement in school activities aligned with research, promoting a more supportive and achieving school community. Additionally, SBM encouraged the proactive adoption of educational innovations, making schools more adaptable and responsive to evolving student needs.

Furthermore, SBM empowered parents and teachers to have a stronger voice in shaping school policies, emphasizing shared governance principles. This led to policies better reflecting the needs of the school community. SBM also promoted proactive community engagement, strengthening unity and support for educational improvement. Lastly, SBM enhanced accountability by emphasizing transparency and shared responsibility, fostering a focus on results and continuous improvement at all levels. The participants' insights resonated with the broader literature, highlighting SBM's potential to transform schools and improve student outcomes positively.

This assumption parallels the study of Bandur et al. (2022), which highlighted the importance of collaborative decision-making and the sense of collective ownership that SBM encourages. This collaborative spirit is crucial for building trust and improving school relationships. Additionally, it underlines how SBM encourages schools to set clear educational objectives and prioritize student learning outcomes, leading to improved academic performance. Moreover, it underscores how SBM empowers stakeholders to participate in decision-making and development, resulting in policies that better reflect the school community's needs. Furthermore, it explores the importance of community engagement in creating a supportive environment for educational improvement.

Initial Expectations About SBM. The participants' initial expectations regarding School-Based Management (SBM) closely paralleled SBM's fundamental principles and aims. They foresaw SBM as a catalyst for empowering teachers and stakeholders in decision-making, in harmony with SBM's core goal of decentralizing authority and fostering collaborative governance. Anticipations included enhanced transparency in budget management, consistent with SBM's focus on financial openness, with the vision of making financial data more accessible to stakeholders. Additionally, participants hoped for increased parental involvement in their children's education, echoing SBM's dedication to family and community engagement, which encourages active parental participation to cultivate a more supportive educational environment. The expectation of more significant opportunities for teachers to share their ideas and participate in decision-making reflected SBM's collaborative ethos, empowering teachers to contribute significantly to school improvement initiatives.

Moreover, participants also envisioned SBM as a means to give voice to parents and stakeholders, aligning with SBM's emphasis on shared decision-making and active engagement from all members of the school community. The aspiration for in-depth discussions on educational policies and strategies resonated with SBM's objective of augmenting the efficacy of educational programs through critical evaluation and adaptability. Lastly, the expectation of deeper leadership engagement within the school aligned with SBM's goal of building leadership capacity at all levels. SBM encourages school leaders to involve teachers and other stakeholders in leadership roles, promoting distributed leadership and collective decision-making.

This assumption parallels the study of Berhanu (2023), who stated that expectation resonates with the central tenet of SBM, which decentralizes decision-making authority from central authorities to individual schools. Additionally, it emphasizes that SBM aims to enhance the involvement of school-level actors in decision-making processes, leading to increased ownership of educational initiatives. Moreover, it highlights that one of the critical features of SBM is allocating financial responsibilities to schools, which should lead to greater transparency and efficiency in resource allocation.

Coping Mechanism of Stakeholders in the Implementation of School-Based Management (SBM). Five major themes emerged from the data collected on the challenges experienced by stakeholders in SBM; these themes: conflict resolution within the SBM framework, balancing SBM responsibilities with other obligations, innovative approaches to improve SBM processes, and seeking support and guidance during challenging times.

Conflict Resolution within SBM Framework. The participants' acknowledgment of conflicts within the School-Based Management (SBM) framework highlighted the complex nature of collaborative decision-making and resource allocation. These conflicts, though challenging, were not uncommon in educational settings, and their presence underscored the importance of effective conflict resolution strategies within SBM. Firstly, conflicts that arose in budget allocation indicated that stakeholders had differing views on how financial resources should be distributed. This was a recurring challenge in SBM, as it involved deciding which projects and initiatives should receive funding. Research in educational leadership emphasized the need for transparent and inclusive budgeting processes that involved all stakeholders to mitigate conflicts.

Secondly, disagreements regarding project prioritization and educational priorities could have stemmed from varying perspectives on what initiatives would have the most significant impact on student outcomes. Conflict in these areas emphasized the need for clear criteria and decision-making frameworks to guide project selection and prioritization, as outlined in SBM principles. Thirdly, conflicts during planning activities and aligning ideas in meetings may have resulted from differences in vision or interpretation of school goals. Effective communication and collaborative problem-solving were essential to address these conflicts constructively and ensure that plans aligned with the school's overall mission and objectives. Lastly, differing opinions regarding the allocation of funds highlighted

the challenge of balancing competing needs and interests within SBM. It underscored the importance of establishing shared goals and priorities to guide resource allocation decisions and mechanisms for resolving conflicts when they arose.

This assumption parallels the study of Malimban (2019), who stated that educational leadership and SBM emphasize the need for transparent budgeting processes that involve all stakeholders. Conflict resolution strategies, such as consensus-building and prioritization criteria, have been recommended in the literature to address these issues. Additionally, disagreements over project prioritization and educational priorities are common in SBM, as stakeholders may have varying perspectives on what initiatives will benefit students most, and conflicts arising during planning activities and strategy development often stem from differing visions or interpretations of school goals. Moreover, it emphasizes the importance of shared decision-making processes that involve stakeholders in setting goals and priorities.

Balancing SBM Responsibilities with Other Obligations. Balancing School-Based Management (SBM) responsibilities with other obligations is a critical aspect of ensuring the effectiveness of SBM implementation, and the strategies shared by the participants aligned with well-established principles of time management and work-life balance. These strategies reflect a proactive approach to managing their roles effectively. Additionally, participants stressed the importance of maintaining work-life balance, recognizing that excessive workloads can lead to burnout and negatively impact their well-being. Similarly, practical time management tools such as calendars and to-do lists were highlighted, illustrating their commitment to allocating time efficiently between teaching and SBM responsibilities.

Moreover, participants mentioned the prioritization of responsibilities, underlining the significance of setting priorities and focusing on high-impact tasks. Balancing attending SBM meetings with prioritizing a child's education highlights the significance of family commitments. Furthermore, acknowledging the importance of coordination and communication underscored the collaborative nature of SBM and its reliance on effective communication and coordination to achieve shared goals. The participants represented a comprehensive approach to balancing SBM responsibilities with other obligations, incorporating principles of time management, work-life balance, and effective communication while drawing from established literature in education.

This assumption parallels the study of Martin (2019), who emphasized the importance of maintaining a work-life balance by allocating specific time for family and self. Research in education underscores the significance of educators' well-being and highlights that a healthy work-life balance positively impacts job satisfaction and overall productivity. Time management tools such as calendars and to-do lists resonate with the literature emphasizing the role of effective time management in educational settings. Educators often face time constraints due to their teaching commitments, making time management essential for fulfilling additional roles like SBM leadership. Moreover, self-care practices can help reduce stress and burnout, ultimately benefiting personal and professional life.

Innovative Approaches to Improve SBM Processes. These innovative approaches represented a concerted effort to improve the educational institution's School-Based Management (SBM) processes. By embracing financial tracking and management technology, the school adopted a more streamlined and transparent approach to its financial operations. Regular Parent-Teacher Conferences and interactive workshops demonstrated a commitment to actively involving parents in their child's education, fostering collaboration between home and school. Using storytelling as a communication tool was a creative way to ensure that all stakeholders, including teachers, parents, and students, could better understand the school's plans and goals. Establishing an online collaboration platform led to more efficient and dynamic communication among staff, parents, and students, ultimately promoting unity within the school community.

Additionally, implementing an online portal for parental engagement signified a dedication to maintaining open and continuous dialogue with parents, providing them valuable insights into their child's education. Furthermore, developing a teacher mentoring program highlighted the school's commitment to professional development and support for its educators. By pairing experienced teachers with newer ones, this program facilitated the exchange of knowledge and best practices, ultimately enhancing teaching quality. These innovative approaches represented a comprehensive effort to optimize SBM processes, ensuring a more engaged and effective educational environment.

This assumption parallels the study of Jihan (2023) with established literature in educational management, parental involvement, communication strategies, collaborative decision-making, and professional development. These approaches, which encompass embracing technology for financial management, fostering regular Parent-Teacher Conferences, utilizing storytelling for communication, establishing online collaboration platforms, implementing online portals for parental engagement, and developing teacher mentoring programs, have been recognized as effective means to enhance SBM processes and create a more engaged and effective educational environment. This alignment with existing literature underscores their potential to improve educational outcomes and foster a stronger school community.

Seeking Support and Guidance during Challenging Times. In times of challenge and uncertainty, educational leaders demonstrated a proactive approach to School-Based Management (SBM) by seeking support and guidance through various strategic practices. Within the school, the SBM team was pivotal in fostering collaborative decision-making, emphasizing shared responsibilities, and collectively addressing complex issues. Additionally, a mentor in educational leadership provided school leaders with a valuable resource for guidance and expertise, enabling them to navigate challenges effectively.

Similarly, beyond the school's boundaries, engagement with the Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) exemplified a commitment to include parents as essential partners in the educational process. This involvement facilitated valuable feedback and strengthened the sense of community within the school. Internally, the SBM coordinator's role as a mentor and adviser was instrumental in supporting and guiding new leaders, ensuring a smooth transition into their roles and an understanding of SBM processes. Moreover, seeking advice from fellow SBM leaders in other schools and engaging with the school's SBM council encouraged collaboration and transparency, aligning decisions with the school's overarching goals and values.

Furthermore, establishing a mentorship program for SBM leaders promoted ongoing professional development and knowledge sharing within the school community. Lastly, creating an SBM network within the local community strengthened connections among schools, enabling them to collaborate, share resources, and extend mutual support during challenging times. Collectively, these practices reflected a commitment to effective SBM, professional growth, and inclusive decision-making, ultimately contributing to the resilience and success of the school community.

This assumption parallels the study of Ogunode and Chijindu (2022), who stated that the concept of collaborative decision-making within SBM teams is widely acknowledged. It emphasizes the importance of distributed leadership within schools. Collaborative teams ensure a broader range of perspectives and expertise, which is precious during challenging situations. Additionally, mentorship in educational leadership is a well-documented practice, and it discusses how mentor-mentee relationships benefit school leaders by providing guidance, advice, and valuable insights, particularly during challenging phases in their leadership roles. The idea of seeking advice and support from peers is well-documented in the context of professional learning communities. Educators sharing experiences and strategies within communities of practice can help schools navigate challenging situations.

Insights of Stakeholders in the Implementation of School-Based Management (SBM) Leadership and Governance. Three major themes emerged from the data collected on stakeholders' insights in SBM: transparency and communication within SB, collaboration, and improvement.

Transparency and Communication with SBM. In school management, transparency and effective communication are integral. Transparency builds trust by openly sharing financial details and decision-making processes, while inclusive decision-making ensures all stakeholders have a voice. Open communication fosters engagement, and financial transparency promotes accountability. Efficient communication and data analysis tools enhance information flow, and ongoing efforts to promote transparency embed these principles in the school's culture, fostering trust and collaboration among all stakeholders.

This assumption parallels the study of Silabay and Alegre (2023), who consistently highlight the pivotal role of transparency and communication in effective school management. Transparency fosters trust among stakeholders, while inclusive decision-making ensures collective engagement and ownership. Open communication is integral to building trust and mutual understanding, and financial transparency promotes informed resource allocation. The use of efficient communication tools and data analysis supports data-driven decision-making. Promoting transparency as an ongoing effort is crucial for embedding these principles within the school's culture. Overall, the literature underscores the enduring importance of these practices in enhancing school management and community engagement.

Collaboration of Stakeholders In SBM. Active involvement of parents and the community was widely recognized as a cornerstone of effective school management. Parents' engagement in their children's education positively influenced students' academic performance, behavior, and overall well-being. Likewise, community involvement brought valuable resources, expertise, and support to the school, enriching the educational experience. Collaboration among various stakeholders, including the School-Based Management (SBM) team, teachers, parents, and community members, was essential for successful school management. Such collaboration led to improved school performance and better decision-making processes. When these groups worked cohesively, they brought diverse perspectives and skills, enabling more effective problem-solving and decision-making.

Continuous efforts to enhance parent and community engagement were vital for the school's overall success. Increased engagement resulted in better student outcomes, higher attendance rates, and improved school climates. Schools that actively sought ways to involve parents and the community created stronger partnerships and a more supportive educational environment. This assumption parallels the study of Tansiri and Bong (2019), who emphasized the significance of shared leadership within SBM teams; they found that effective SBM teams distributed leadership responsibilities among members, fostering collaboration and collective decision-making. Such shared leadership positively influenced school performance. Their findings highlight that successful SBM teams functioned as cohesive units characterized by open communication, mutual respect, and a shared commitment to school improvement. Collaborative decision-making within these teams lead to more effective strategies for addressing educational challenges.

Improvement. The statements collectively conveyed a commitment to enhancing various aspects of the educational institution's operations and outcomes. The focus on strengthening the financial literacy of stakeholders underscored the importance of informed decision-making and financial responsibility in the organization. Deeper parent engagement signified a positive shift towards more involved and supportive families, which could significantly impact the educational experience. The call for continuous improvement in SBM projects and activities reflected an organization's adaptability and commitment to providing the best educational services. Improved education quality, a central goal, indicated a dedication to enhancing all facets of the educational experience. Lastly, the

emphasis on performance metrics and accountability underscored the need for evidence-based decision-making and resource allocation to drive the institution toward achieving its educational objectives.

This assumption parallels the study of Tomaszewski et al. (2020), who indicate that when stakeholders, including parents and community members, clearly understand school finances, they can more effectively participate in budget decisions and financial oversight. This contributes to the overall success of SBM. Additionally, the acknowledgment of the need for continuous improvement aligns with the adaptive nature of SBM. Scholars emphasize the importance of ongoing evaluation and refinement of SBM initiatives to ensure they remain effective and responsive to changing educational needs.

Conclusion

School-Based Management (SBM) was a dynamic and collaborative approach to educational leadership and governance that involved various stakeholders, including teachers, parents, and community members. While SBM held great promise for improving educational outcomes and fostering a sense of ownership among school communities, it was not without its challenges. One of the foremost challenges in SBM was effective time management, particularly for teachers who had to balance their teaching responsibilities with SBM duties. This time constraint could impact the depth of engagement in SBM processes. Additionally, securing active participation from parents and ensuring clear communication within the school community were essential but often challenging aspects of SBM.

However, SBM participants brought valuable experience and dedication to their roles, with some having been involved for several years. Their commitment to collaborative decision-making and continuous improvement in education was a driving force for the success of SBM. As educational institutions continued to embrace SBM as a means to enhance school governance and leadership, addressing these challenges while capitalizing on the expertise and dedication of SBM participants remained crucial. Through effective time management, strategies to engage parents, improved communication, and ongoing professional development, SBM could realize its potential in shaping the future of education and fostering more robust, more inclusive school communities.

Overall, to excel in School-Based Management (SBM), as a teacher, should focus on enhancing time management skills, engaging parents effectively, improving communication within the school community, and investing in continuous professional development. These strategies would help them navigate challenges and maximize SBM's potential to improve educational outcomes and build inclusive school communities.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Judelyn P. Malasaga

General Santos City National Secondary School of Arts and Trades
Department of Education – Philippines

Francisco M. Espinosa, EdD, PhD, LPT

Lagao National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Geraldine D. Rodriguez, PhD, EdD, LPT

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges – Philippines